

Manual for CESM2 CMIP6/CFMIP3-Tier2 simulations

Scope: This document is designed to summarize the methods used to perform the CMIP6/CFMIP3 Tier-2 simulations with NCAR's CESM version 2. Note that some of the files were created using 'cmip6' user and may be restricted.

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README (description of files)

An archive snapshot of data files and scripts that were used to create the CESM2 CFMIP simulations is available to the user. We define **\$ARCHROOT** as the root archive directory downloaded from zenodo.com. **\$ARCHROOT** contains the following subdirectories organized as follows:

1. **case_directories**: An archive snapshot of the collection of CESM2 case directories for all CESM2 CFMIP simulations. Case directories include simulation configuration and software environment settings.
2. **CFMIP**: Contains user-generated support files implemented when running the CESM2 CFMIP simulations. Subdirectories include:
 - a. **user_bc_files**: Boundary conditions files needed by certain simulations
 - b. **user_init_files**: Component initialization files needed by certain simulations
 - c. **user_namelist_modifications**: Customized component namelist files (user_nl_*) and source code modifications (SourceMods/src.*) used by certain simulations
3. **scripts_cylc**: Subdirectories contain the cylc workflow scripts that were used to run the CESM2 CFMIP simulations. [Cylc](#) is a workflow engine designed to manage large, coordinated simulation efforts.
4. **input_support_files**: Customized NCL and python scripts and associated data files used to create input files for certain CESM CFMIP simulations.

Useful directories (as of July 2020)

- **Instructions:** <https://cesm-wf-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>
- CFMIP run catalog (login credentials required):
<https://csegweb.cgd.ucar.edu/expdb2.0/cgi-bin/expList.cgi>
- Where create_cylc_newcase scripts reside: `$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc`
- Input data directories: `$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_*`
- CFMIP case directories (as originally run):
`/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/$CASENAME`
- CFMIP case directories (as archived):
`$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`
- Preliminary output (as originally run):
`/glade/scratch/cmip6/archive/$CASENAME`
- Raw run directory (pre- short-term archiving): `/glade/scratch/cmip6/$CASENAME/run`

- CESM2 timing chart (for PE layout):
<https://csegweb.cgd.ucar.edu/timing/cgi-bin/timings.cgi>

cylc workflow notes

- **Instructions:** <https://cesm-wf-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>
- **Access:** `sudox cmip6` (passwd: *use yubikey*)... **DO THIS BEFORE CREATING CASE, SETTING UP CASE, AND BUILDING THE MODEL**
- **Paths:**
 - Where `create_cylc_newcase` scripts reside:
\$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc
- To view reserved case: <https://csegweb.cgd.ucar.edu/expdb2.0> and click on "MIP experiments"
- On Cheyenne (**with `sudox cmip6`**): `cd /gpfs/u/home/cmip6/$user/CESM-WF`
- **THE FOLLOWING INSTRUCTIONS PRIMARILY USE "piSST" AS AN EXAMPLE**
- Create new copy of `create_cylc_newcase`:
`cp create_cylc_newcase create_cylc_newcase_piSST`
- Optional settings in `create_cylc_newcase_piSST`:
 - `GENERATE_AVGS_* = 'FALSE'`
 - `GENERATE_DIAGS_* = 'FALSE'`
 - Check `cesm_code_base`, we primarily used:
`'/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp007'`
- Best to ensure that staged files are set by this point:
 - Staged boundary conditions files (e.g., SSTICE*):
`/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME`
 - Staged component initialization files (e.g., *.cam.i.*, *.clm2.r.*):
`/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME`
 - Staged namelist files (e.g., user_nl_cam, user_nl_clm):
`/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/$CASENAME`
- The 'create_newcase' equivalent (piSST example):

```
./create_cylc_newcase_piSST --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.00
1 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset
1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV
--run-unsupported --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850_
BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001
```

- **[Optional: To change project number]** The project number used for the simulations CANNOT be changed using either "--project Pxxxxxxx" when invoking 'create_cylc_newcase' -or- by adding 'PROJECT': Pxxxxxxx as a key-value pair within the cesm_xml section of the create_cylc_newcase file. Instead: in /glade/u/home/cmip6/cylc_suites/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001/suite.rc **change all '-A' options to the desired project number**
 - **Should also run the following in the case directory, to be consistent:**

```
cd
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001
.xmlchange PROJECT="Pxxxxxxx"
.xmlchange CHARGE_ACCOUNT="Pxxxxxxx"
```
 - Must then "register" modified suite.rc using (can do this from any dir), see command below
- **[Optional]** To change requested job wallclock time... in /glade/u/home/cmip6/cylc_suites/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001/suite.rc, make the following change:

OLD: execution time limit = PT12H (for 12:00 request, ~L51? Depends on # jobs)

NEW: execution time limit = PT6H (for 6:00 request)

 - Must then "register" modified suite.rc using (can do this from any dir):

```
cylc register $CASENAME.suite.cmip6
/glade/u/home/cmip6/cylc_suites/$CASENAME
... e.g.:
cylc register
f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001.suite.cmip6
/glade/u/home/cmip6/cylc_suites/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001
```
- **[Optional]** To change requested job queue... in /glade/u/home/cmip6/cylc_suites/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001, make the following change:

OLD: -q = regular (~L55, but depends on # of lined-up job submissions)

NEW: -q = economy

 - Must then "register" modified suite.rc using (can do this from any dir):

```
cylc register $CASENAME.suite.cmip6
/glade/u/home/cmip6/cylc_suites/$CASENAME
... e.g.:
cylc register
f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001.suite.cmip6
/glade/u/home/cmip6/cylc_suites/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001
```
- cd /glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001
- **[Specific to amip-p4k-lwoff]** I was not able to change SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME directly through create_cylc_newcase for some unknown reason, so instead I had to run the following command from the case directory:

- `./xmlchange`
`SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME="/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_bc_files/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-p4k-lwoff.001/cfmip_sst_p4k_HadOIB1_bc_0.9x1.25_1850_2017_c20190129.nc"`
- **Setup the case:** `./case.setup`
- **[Optional]** Run `./preview_namelists` to see what the final settings will be in `CaseDocs/*_in`
- **Build the model:** `./case.build`
- **To invoke gcylc command:**
`gcylc f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001.suite.cmip6`
 (found in `cylc "Instructions"` file noted at end of running `./create_cylc_newcase` command)
- **In cylc GUI:** Click on `Run` button → have `cold start` be checked → click `Start`
 - Dates listed are end dates of job
 - To pause, right-click on next run job and select `Hold`
- **To return to GUI,** resubmit `gcylc` command
- **Can close cylc GUI at any time:** `File` → `Exit`

Case-specific notes

(See Table of Contents at top of document for listing of simulations)

- **piSST**
 - **Directive:** "An AGCM experiment with monthly varying SSTs, sea ice, atmospheric constituents and any other necessary boundary conditions (e.g. vegetation if required) taken from each model's own piControl run (using the 30 years of pi-Control that are parallel to years 111–140 of its abrupt4xCO2 run). Dynamic vegetation should be turned off in the whole piSST set of experiments."
 - **Related case(s)**
 - **pi-Control**
 - **case directory:**
`/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/cesm2.1-exp003/b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-piControl.001`
 - **Case details:**
 - Case location: `$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`
 - Case name: `f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001`

- **Create_newcase command:**

```
./create_cylc_newcase_piSST --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.0
01 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset
1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV
--run-unsupported --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850
_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001
```

- **A note on SSTICE_YEAR_*:** Years 111-140 of abrupt4xCO2 correspond to years 611-640 of piControl (piControl's start date is 0501-01-01). The SST and sea ice forcing data set must therefore span (at minimum) this time window. The NCL script used to generate

SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME lower boundary forcing is:

\$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/make_cfmip-tier2-piSST_bc_forcing.ncl and produces SSTICE forcing file:

```
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_bc_files/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f
09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001. The NCL script ensures that the correct
SST and sea ice data are staged. Given this NCL script and output file,
the corresponding settings for the piSST case are:
```

```
RUN_STARTDATE="0001-01-01"
```

```
SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN="1"
```

```
SSTICE_YEAR_START="611"
```

```
SSTICE_YEAR_END="645"
```

- **Configuration settings**

- **Compset:** used long-string form mimicking piControl but with CICE%PRES and DOCN%DOM (decided against making new compset)
 - 1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV

- **RUN_TYPE:** startup (used by default)

- **PE layout:** used default

- **COSP:** Active. In user_nl_cam, add `set docosp = .true.` (runs -all- COSP simulators). Some COSP outputs automatically added to history file streams, other COSP outputs added to default list via user_nl_cam. **Note that COSP is active for all CFMIP Tier-2 runs with CESM2.**

- **Model component initializations:**

- **CAM:**

```
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_init_files/f.e21.F1850_BG
C.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001/b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-
piControl.001.cam.i.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

- **CLM:**

```
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_init_files/f.e21.F1850_BG
C.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001/b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-
piControl.001.clm2.r.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

- Other components: leave unset
- XML changes -before- ./case.setup
 - ./xmlchange --append CAM_CONFIG_OPTS="-co2_cycle -cosp"
- XML changes after ./case.setup
 - ./xmlchange CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS=" co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true. "
 - ./xmlchange
SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME="\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/\$CASENAME/sstice_fv0.9x1.25_piSST_0610-0645mod.nc"
 - ./xmlchange RUN_STARTDATE="0001-01-01"
 - ./xmlchange SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN="1"
 - ./xmlchange SSTICE_YEAR_START="611"
 - ./xmlchange SSTICE_YEAR_END="645"
- CAM output fields: includes all fields from CFMIP Tier-1 amip-4xCO2 simulation, plus a few selected additional fields
 - Look at
\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-4xCO2.001 for outputs
- CLM output fields: includes all fields from CFMIP Tier-1 amip-4xCO2 simulation
 - Look at user_nl_clm from
\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-4xCO2.001
- NCL script to generate SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME lower boundary forcing:


```
$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/make_cfmip-tier2-piSST_bc_forcing.ncl
```

 - Produces SSTICE forcing file: "SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME" value="\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST.001"
- "RUN_STARTDATE" value="0001-01-01"
- "SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN" value="1"
 - See thread: <https://bb.cgd.ucar.edu/align> for more.

- **piSST-pxK**

- **Directive:** "Same as piSST, but with a spatially and temporally uniform SST anomaly applied on top of the monthly varying piSST SSTs. The magnitude of the uniform increase is taken from each model's global, climatological annual mean open SST change between abrupt4xCO2 minus piControl (using the mean of years 111–140 of abrupt4xCO2 and the parallel 30-year section of piControl)."
- **Related case(s)**
 - **pi-Control**
 - (see piSST above for details of pi-Control)
 - **abrupt4xCO2**
 - **case directory:**
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.BCO2x4cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt4xCO2.001
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name: f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-pxK.001
 - Create_newcase command:
./create_cylc_newcase_piSST-pxK --case /glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-pxK.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset 1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV --run-unsupported --user-mods-dir /gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-pxK.001
- **Configuration settings**
 - **user_bc_files**
 - A modified version of SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME was created using NCL script

`$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/make_cfmip-tier2-piSST-pxK_b
c_forcing.ncl` following the case directives. This script creates file
`sstice_fv0.9x1.25_piSST-pxK_0610-0645mod.nc` which can be
found in: `$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME`

- **user_init_files**

- `*cam.i.*` and `*clm2.r.*` init files (CAM and CLM init) will be identical to those used in piSST and saved as:

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME/b.e21.B1850.f09_g  
17.CMIP6-piControl.001.cam.i.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

and

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME/b.e21.B1850.f09_g  
17.CMIP6-piControl.001.clm2.r.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

- **user_namelist_modifications**

- Both `user_nl_cam` and `user_nl_clm` will be identical to those used in piSST **--EXCEPT--** for one change to `user_nl_cam` and one change to `user_nl_clm`:
- (1) In `user_nl_cam`, changed the directory of `ncdata` from 'piSST' to 'piSST-pxK'
- (2) In `user_nl_clm`, also changed the directory of `finidat` from 'piSST' to 'piSST-pxK'
- These namelist files can be found in

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/$CASENAME
```

- **create_cylc_newcase_*** (alternate method to modify namelist settings during `create_newcase` step... other method is through `user_nl_*` in `user-mods-dir`)

- `cesm_xml` settings were copied from piSST:
 - `"SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN" value="1"`
 - `"SSTICE_YEAR_START" value="611"`
 - `"SSTICE_YEAR_END" value="645"`
 - `SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME =`
`"$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME/sstice_fv0.9
x1.25_piSST-pxK_0610-0645mod.nc"`

- **piSST-4xCO2-rad**

- **Directive:** "Same as piSST, but CO2 as seen by the radiation scheme (but not the land model) is quadrupled."
- **Related case(s)**
 - **piSST (see above)**
 - **pi-Control**
 - (see piSST above for details of pi-Control)
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: `$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`

- Case name:
f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-4xCO2-rad.001

- Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_piSST-4xCO2-rad --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-4
xCO2-rad.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset
1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV
--run-unsupported --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850
_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-4xCO2-rad.001
```

- Configuration settings

- User_bc_files (in /gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/)

- SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME will be identical to that used in piSST but with a file name change:

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME/sstice_fv0.9x1.25_p
iSST-4xCO2-rad_0610-0645mod.nc
```

- user_init_files

- *cam.i.* and *clm2.r.* init files (CAM and CLM init) will be identical to those used in piSST and are saved as:

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME/b.e21.B1850.f09_g
17.CMIP6-piControl.001.cam.i.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

and

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME/b.e21.B1850.f09_g
17.CMIP6-piControl.001.clm2.r.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

- user_namelist_modifications

- Both user_nl_cam and user_nl_clm will be identical to those used in piSST **--EXCEPT--** for two changes to user_nl_cam and one change to user_nl_clm:

- (1) In user_nl_cam, needed to add the following line to properly set atmospheric CO2 to 4x PI levels (PI level = 287.4e-6) for the radiation scheme only (the land model needs to continue to see PI CO2 levels):

```
co2vmr_rad = 1138.8e-6
```

- **DO NOT** set CCSM_CO2_PPMV = 1138.8 in create_cylc_newcase* (which sets it in env_run.xml) because this will change CO2 level in CLM, which is not what we want to do here... see comment on CO2 quadrupling below)

- (2) In user_nl_cam, also changed the directory of ncdat from 'piSST' to 'piSST-4xCO2-rad'
- (3) In user_nl_clm, also changed the directory of finidat from 'piSST' to 'piSST-4xCO2-rad'
- (4) Note: In user_nl_clm, allow co2_type to remain at its default value ('diagnostic')
- These namelist files can be found in

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/$CASENAME
```

- **create_cylc_newcase_* important settings:**
 - "SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN" value="611"
 - "SSTICE_YEAR_START" value="611"
 - "SSTICE_YEAR_END" value="645"
- **CO2 quadrupling:**
 - To use 4xCO2 levels (1138.8e-6) for atm but PI CO2 levels (284.7e-6) for lnd, use the procedure above in the user_namelist_modifications section. Note that setting CCSM_CO2_PPMV=1138.8 in create_cylc_newcase_piSST-4xCO2-rad should **not** be done because this will erroneously set 4xCO2 in CLM.
 - The following CO2 settings should be confirmed:
 - env_run: CCSM_BGC = CO2A
 - atm_in: co2vmr = 284.7e-6 and co2vmr_rad = 1138.8e-6
 - lnd_in: co2_type = diagnostic, and in the bottom command-line listing check:
 - -co2_ppmv 284.7e-6
 - -co2_type diagnostic

● piSST-4xCO2

- **Directive:** "Same as piSST, but CO2 is quadrupled. The increase in CO2 is seen by both the radiation scheme and vegetation."
- **Related case(s)**
 - **piSST (see above)**
 - **pi-Control**
 - (see piSST above for details of pi-Control)
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name: f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-4xCO2.001
 - Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_piSST-4xCO2 --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-4
xCO2.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset
1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV
--run-unsupported --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850
_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-piSST-4xCO2.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - User_bc_files (in /gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/)
 - SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME will be identical to that used in piSST but with a file name change:

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME/sstice_fv0.9x1.25_p
iSST-4xCO2_0610-0645mod.nc
```
 - user_init_files

- *cam.i.* and *clm2.r.* init file (CAM and CLM init) will be identical to that used in piSST and are saved as:

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME/b.e21.B1850.f09_g
17.CMIP6-piControl.001.cam.i.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

and

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME/b.e21.B1850.f09_g
17.CMIP6-piControl.001.clm2.r.0611-01-01-00000.nc
```

■ user_namelist_modifications

- Both user_nl_cam and user_nl_clm will be identical to those used in piSST **--EXCEPT--** for two changes to user_nl_cam and one change to user_nl_clm:
- (1) In user_nl_cam, needed to add the following line to properly set atmospheric CO2 to 4x PI levels (PI level = 287.4e-6):

```
co2vmr = 1138.8e-6
```

- I think this was necessary because 1850_cam6 use case seemed to supercede CCSM_CO2_PPMV setting via env_run.xml (as set by create_cylc_newcase*... see comment on CO2 quadrupling below)
- (2) In user_nl_cam, also changed the directory of ncdat from 'piSST' to 'piSST-4xCO2'
- (3) In user_nl_clm, also changed the directory of finidat from 'piSST' to 'piSST-4xCO2'
- These namelist files can be found in

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/$CASENAME
```

■ create_cylc_newcase_* important settings:

- "SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN" value="611"
- "SSTICE_YEAR_START" value="611"
- "SSTICE_YEAR_END" value="645"

■ CO2 quadrupling:

- At first I tried setting "CCSM_CO2_PPMV" value="1138.8" (4 x 284.7) in create_cylc_newcase_piSST-4xCO2 (via env_run.xml), but it appeared that the 1850_cam6 "use case" supercedes this (and so co2vmr remained at 284.7e-6 in atm_in). To correct this, I then tried adding "co2vmr = 1138.8e-6" in user_nl_cam and this had the desired effect of setting co2vmr = 1138.8e-6 in atm_in. I then changed co2vmr in usermods_dir as well. Even when using "CCSM_CO2_PPMV" value="1138.8" in create_cylc_newcase_piSST-4xCO2, it appeared that the CO2 setting in Ind_in was correct: "-co2_ppmv 1138.8 -co2_type diagnostic" as shown in the command-line version. Regarding co2_type = diagnostic, Brian Mederios and I agree that this is the correct setting for all runs.
- The following CO2 settings should be confirmed:
 - env_run: CCSM_BGC = CO2A

- atm_in: co2vmr
- lnd_in: co2_type = diagnostic, and in the bottom command-line listing check:
 - -co2_ppmv 1138.8
 - -co2_type diagnostic

● a4SST

- **Directive:** "As for piSST, but with monthly varying SSTs taken from years 111 to 140 of each model's own abrupt4xCO2 experiment instead of from piControl. Sea ice is unchanged from piSST."
- **Related cases(s)**
 - **pi-Control**
 - (see piSST above for details of pi-Control)
 - **abrupt4xCO2**
 - (see piSST-pxK above for details of abrupt4xCO2)
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name: f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SST.001
 - Create_newcase command:


```
./create_cylc_newcase_a4SST --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SST.0
01 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset
1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV
--run-unsupported --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850
_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SST.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - user_bc_files
 - A modified version of SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME was created using NCL script


```
$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/make_cfmip-tier2-a4SST_bc_forcing.ncl
```

 following the case directives. This script creates file sstice_fv0.9x1.25_a4SST_SSTyr0110-0145mod_ICEyr0610-0645mod.nc which can be found in:


```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME
```
 - NOTE1: Lower boundary forcing files ("sstice_*") with "mod" appended to date range indicate that the file has been modified to accommodate the model's tendency to "cycle back" to the final time step of the file during interpolation. Thus, in "mod" files the year prior to the simulation initialization date is copied to the final year of all data arrays such that CESM's time interpolation scheme works correctly from the beginning of the simulation.

- NOTE2: Timing convention of data within this file is made to follow SST [even though SST is from Y111-140 of abrupt4xCO2 and sea ice is from Y611-640 (actually 610-645 with buffers included)]: thus, the file time stamps run Y110-145.
- user_init_files
 - Init files for CAM & CLM will be taken from the abrupt4xCO2 case to reduce shock of initialization given the significantly warmer SSTs in that run compared to piControl. These files can be found in: \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/\$CASENAME
- user_namelist_files: As in piSST, but CAM initialization file is specified via 'ncdata' entry in user_nl_cam and CLM initialization files is specified via 'finidat' entry in user_nl_clm. See \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_files/\$CASENAME
- create_cylc_newcase_* important settings:
 - RUN_STARTDATE="0001-01-01"
 - SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN="1"
 - SSTICE_YEAR_START="111"
 - SSTICE_YEAR_END="145"

● a4SSTice

- **Directive:** "As for piSST, but with monthly varying SSTs and sea ice taken from years 111 to 140 of each model's own abrupt4xCO2 experiment instead of from piControl."
- **Related cases(s)**
 - **pi-Control**
 - (see piSST above for details of pi-Control)
 - **abrupt4xCO2**
 - (see piSST-pxK above for details of abrupt4xCO2)
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name: f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SSTice.001
 - Create_newcase command:


```
./create_cylc_newcase_a4SSTice --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SSTice.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset
1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV
--run-unsupported --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SSTice.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - user_bc_files
 - A modified version of SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME was created using NCL script

`$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/make_cfmip-tier2-a4SSTice_bc_forcing.ncl` following the case directives. This script creates file `sstice_fv0.9x1.25_a4SSTice_SSTyr0110-0145mod_ICEyr0110-0145mod.nc` which can be found in:

`$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME`

- NOTE: Timing convention of data within this file is made to follow SST, although SIC for a4SSTice uses an identical time window. The nominal analysis window is Y0111-140, but due to data buffering and restrictions of initialization files I will use a specified window of Y110-145.
- A note on `SSTICE_YEAR_*`: The time stamps set in the SSTICE lower boundary forcing file for a4SSTice correspond to the abrupt4xCO2 time window.
- **user_init_files**
 - Init files for CAM & CLM will be taken from the abrupt4xCO2 case to reduce shock of initialization given the significantly warmer SSTs in that run compared to piControl. These files can be found in: `$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/$CASENAME`
- **user_namelist_files**: As in piSST, but CAM initialization file is specified via 'ncdata' entry in `user_nl_cam` and CLM initialization files is specified via 'finidat' entry in `user_nl_clm`. See `$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_files/$CASENAME`
- **create_cylc_newcase_*** important settings:
 - `RUN_STARTDATE="0001-01-01"`
 - `SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN="1"`
 - `SSTICE_YEAR_START="111"`
 - `SSTICE_YEAR_END="145"`

● a4SSTice-4xCO2

- **Directive**: "As for a4SSTice, but CO2 is quadrupled, and the increase in CO2 is seen by both the radiation scheme and vegetation."
- **Related cases(s)**
 - **pi-Control**
 - (see piSST above for details of pi-Control)
 - **abrupt4xCO2**
 - (see piSST-pxK above for details of abrupt4xCO2)
- **Case details**:
 - Case location: `$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`
 - Case name:
`f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SSTice-4xCO2.001`
 - **Create_newcase** command:
`./create_cylc_newcase_a4SSTice-4xCO2 --case`

```

/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SSTice-4xCO2.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset 1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV --run-unsupported --user-mods-dir /gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-a4SSTice-4xCO2.001

```

○ Configuration settings

■ user_bc_files

- SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME will be identical to that used in a4SSTice but with a file name change... see
\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/\$CASENAME

■ user_init_files

- *cam.i.* and *clm2.r.* init file (CAM and CLM init) will be identical to that used in a4SSTice but with a file name change. See
\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/\$CASENAME

■ user_namelist_modifications

- Both user_nl_cam and user_nl_clm will be identical to those used in a4SSTice **--EXCEPT--** for two changes to user_nl_cam and one change to user_nl_clm:

- (1) In user_nl_cam, add the following line to properly set atmospheric CO2 to 4x PI levels (PI = 287.4e-6):

```
co2vmr = 1138.8e-6
```

- This apparently was necessary because the 1850_cam6 use case seemed to supercede CCSM_CO2_PPMV setting via env_run.xml (as set by create_cylc_newcase*... see comment on CO2 quadrupling below)

- (2) In user_nl_cam, change the directory path of `ncdata` from 'a4SSTice' to 'a4SSTice-4xCO2'

- (3) In user_nl_clm, change the directory path of `finidat` from 'a4SSTice' to 'a4SSTice-4xCO2'

■ create_cylc_newcase_* important settings:

- "SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN" value="1"
- "SSTICE_YEAR_START" value="111"
- "SSTICE_YEAR_END" value="145"

■ Notes on CO2 quadrupling:

- At first I tried setting "CCSM_CO2_PPMV" value="1138.8" (4 x 284.7) in create_cylc_newcase_piSST-4xCO2 (via env_run.xml), but it appeared that the 1850_cam6 use case supercedes this (and so co2vmr remained at 284.7e-6 in atm_in). To correct this, I then tried adding "co2vmr = 1138.8e-6" in user_nl_cam and this had the desired effect of setting co2vmr = 1138.8e-6 in atm_in. I then changed co2vmr in usermods_dir as well. Even when using "CCSM_CO2_PPMV" value="1138.8" in create_cylc_newcase_piSST-4xCO2, it appeared that the CO2

setting in `Ind_in` was correct: `"-co2_ppmv 1138.8 -co2_type diagnostic"` as shown in the command-line version at the bottom of that file. Regarding `co2_type = diagnostic`, Brian Medeiros and I agree that this is the correct setting for all runs.

- A note on `CCSM_BGC`: For all CFMIP simulations using a dynamical ocean ("B" compset), `CCSM_BGC` in `env_run.xml` is set to "CO2C". For all prescribed-SST simulations, `CCSM_BGC = CO2A`. In `piControl`, `CCSM_BGC = CO2C` which would seemingly indicate that CO2 fluxes are sent from both the ocean and land back to the atmosphere model. However, `co2vmr` in either daily or monthly output files from `piControl` indicates a constant `co2vmr = 0.0002847`, so it seems that the `ocn/Ind→atm` CO2 fluxes are ignored.
- The following CO2 settings should be confirmed:
 - `env_run`: `CCSM_BGC = CO2A`
 - `atm_in`: `co2vmr`
 - `Ind_in`: `co2_type = diagnostic`, and in the bottom command-line listing check:
 - `-co2_ppmv 1138.8`
 - `-co2_type diagnostic`

• **amip-a4SST-4xCO2**

- **Directive:** "Same as `amip`, but a patterned SST anomaly is applied on top of the monthly varying `amip` SSTs. This anomaly is a monthly climatology, taken from each model's own `abrupt4xCO2` run minus `piControl` (using the mean of years 111– 140 of `abrupt4xCO2` and the parallel 30-year section of `piControl`). CO2 is quadrupled, and the increase in CO2 is seen by both the radiation scheme and vegetation."
- **Notes:**
 - A note on quadrupling CO2 in an AMIP case: In the PI configurations (e.g., `abrupt2xCO2`), CO2 can be changed by setting `co2vmr` in `CAM_NML_OPTS` in `env_run.xml`. For AMIP runs with evolving CO2, however, the CO2 values must be modified with a boundary file. Such a boundary file was created for `amip-4xCO2`, and this same file will be used for `amip-a4SST-4xCO2`. Background on this: In the `namelist_definition.xml` file, it appears that `co2vmr` or the CO2 specified by the `scenario_ghg` parameter is what is sent to the other components. For `amip-4xCO2` (in `atm_in`), `scenario_ghg = 'CHEM_LBC_FILE'` and `flbc_file = '/glade/work/brianpm/model_data/CFMIP/LBC_1750-2015_CMIP6_GlobAnnA vg_4xCO2_c190228.nc'`. I have copied this file to the CFMIP `user_bc_files` main directory (see "Configuration settings" below). This

4xCO2 is seen by both the radiation and vegetation schemes. In this way, the difference between amip-a4SST-4xCO2 and amip-4xCO2 will be due to the patterned SST anomaly (vs. no SST warming in amip-4xCO2).

- **Related case(s):**
 - **amip (DECK):**
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CMIP6-AMIP.001
 - **amip-4xCO2 (CFMIP):**
\$ARCHROOT/case_directories/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-4xCO2.001
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name:
f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-a4SST-4xCO2.001
 - Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_amip-a4SST-4xCO2 --case  
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-a4  
SST-4xCO2.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset FHIST_BGC --user-mods-dir  
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.FHIST  
_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-a4SST-4xCO2.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - user_bc_files
 - A modified version of the standard AMIP lower boundary forcing file
(/glade/p/cesmdata/cseg/inputdata/atm/cam/sst/sst_HadOIBl_bc_0.9x1.25_1850_2017_c180507.nc) was created:
\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/\$CASENAME/sst_HadOIBl_bc_0.9x1.25_1850_2017_c180507_for_amip-a4SST-4xCO2.nc. The modified file contains SST_cpl that is changed according to the case directive using NCL script
\$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/make_cfmip-tier2-amip-a4SST-4xCO2_bc_forcing.ncl. Note that modified SSTs were set to -1.8°C where ice_cov >= 0.90 (often, ice_cov never reaches 1.0 exactly). Because sea ice cover is -NOT- modified but SSTs are, per the case directive, there are obvious "peculiarities" in the modified forcing file such as sea ice neighboring SSTs that are much above 0°C. This is expected and is similar to the behavior in a4SST.
 - SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME set in env_run.xml should now point to file
\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/\$CASENAME/sst_HadOIBl_bc_0.9x1.25_1850_2017_c180507_for_amip-a4SST-4xCO2.nc.
 - user_init_files

- Nothing to modify: *cam.i.* and *clm2.r.* initialization files (CAM and CLM initialization) will be identical to those used in the amip-4xCO2 experiment, which is set by default for the FHIST compset.
 - user_namelist_modifications
 - Both user_nl_cam and user_nl_clm will be identical to those used in another (arbitrarily chosen) amip-style simulation (e.g., amip-lwoff) **--EXCEPT--** for one change to user_nl_cam: In user_nl_cam, following Brian Medeiros's approach, entry flbc_file should point to file \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/LBC_1750-2015_CMIP6_GlobAnnAvg_4xCO2_c190228.nc to properly set CO2 seen by both the radiation scheme and vegetation to 4x AMIP levels.
 - This file input is required instead of setting co2vmr = 1138.8e-6 in user_nl_cam. Modifying co2vmr should only be used to change CO2 in when CO2 is constant in the run (e.g., PI runs).
 - Note: Ind_in for case amip-4xCO2, I see at the bottom: -co2_ppmv 284.7 -co2_type diagnostic. However, per Brian Medeiros: "In the namelist_definition.xml file, it is clear that co2vmr or the CO2 specified by the scenario_ghg parameter is what is sent to the other components." For amip-4xCO2 the following was used (based on atm_in):


```
flbc_file =
'/glade/work/brianpm/model_data/CFMIP/LBC_1750-2015_CMIP6_GlobAnnAvg_4xCO2_c190228.nc'
scenario_ghg = 'CHEM_LBC_FILE'
```

 ...which indicates that the land model is "seeing" CO2 as modified in flbc_file. Thus, both atm and Ind experience 4xCO2, as desired.
 - create_cylc_newcase_* (alternate method to modify certain namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir). Located in:


```
$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc/CESM-WF_tier2
```

 - cesm_xml settings are identical to those for amip-4xCO2, with one important exception: SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME is specified as noted above in section "user_bc_files".

● amip-piForcing

- **Directive:** "Identical to the amip DECK experiment, but from 1870 to the present with constant pre-industrial forcing levels (anthro & natural)."

- **Note:** Brian Medeiros and I decided, with guidance from Andrews (2014), that we should use the F1850 (full-string) compset and simply change the SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME to the same file used in the amip DECK run.
- **Related case(s):**
 - **amip (DECK):**
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CMIP6-AMIP.001
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name:
f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-piForcing.001
 - Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_amip-piForcing --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.F1850_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-pi
Forcing.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset
1850_CAM60_CLM50%BGC-CROP_CICE%PRES_DOCN%DOM_MOSART_CISM2%NOEVOLVE_SWAV
--run-unsupported --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.F1850
_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-piForcing.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - user_bc_files
 - SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME will be identical to that used in the amip DECK case (/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CMIP6-AMIP.001):
/glade/p/cesmdata/cseg/inputdata/atm/cam/sst/sst_HadOIBI_bc_0.9x1.25_1850_2017_c180507.nc. Because we are using the F1850 compset, however, the model will not point to this file by default. I chose to copy this file into the user_bc_files staging directory rather than point to it directly within CESM's "inputdata" directory, so as to make a more permanent record of the forcing data. See \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/\$CASENAME
 - user_init_files
 - CAM and CLM initialization files (*cam.i.* and *clm2.r.*) will be identical to that used in piSST. See \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_init_files/\$CASENAME
 - user_namelist_modifications
 - user_nl_cam and user_nl_clm are identical to those used for the piSST run. See \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_files/\$CASENAME
 - create_cylc_newcase_* important settings (alternate method to modify namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir):
 - "SSTICE_YEAR_ALIGN" value="1850"
 - "SSTICE_YEAR_START" value="1850"
 - "SSTICE_YEAR_END" value="2016"

- "RUN_STARTDATE" value="1870-01-01"
- The above SSTICE_* settings mimic those of either DECK's amip run or CFMIP's amip-4xCO2 run. Note that the DECK amip, CFMIP amip-4xCO2, and CFMIP amip-piForcing should all use the same SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME. **Note also that RUN_STARTDATE is used to set the initial date for the SST and SIC forcing: amip-4xCO2 used "1979-01-01" and amip (DECK) used "1950-01-01".**
- All other settings: use piSST

● amip-lwoff

- **Directive:** "As for the amip experiment, but with cloud-radiative effects switched off in the LW radiation code."
- **Notes:**
 - Brian Medeiros developed code modifications to activate LWOFF in CESM2. Offline tests were run to confirm accuracy.
 - COSP was not modified to use "lwoff" inputs.
- **Related case(s):**
 - **amip (DECK):**
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CMIP6-AMIP.001
 - **amip-p4k (CFMIP):**
\$ARCHROOT/case_directories/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-p4k.001
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name: f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-lwoff.001
 - Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_amip-lwoff --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-lw
off.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset FHIST_BGC --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fsl/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.FHIST
_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-lwoff.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - user_bc_files: No modifications needed to boundary conditions files (default is acceptable)
 - user_init_files: No modifications needed to initialization files (default is acceptable)
 - user_namelist_modifications
 - user_nl_cam is nearly identical to that used in amip-p4k, except COSP is now activated (docosp = .true.) and a inconsequential bug in fincll (duplicate instance of 'PS:A')

was removed). `user_nl_clm` was copied directly from `amip-p4k` run into the `amip-lwoff` staging directory. See

`$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_files/$CASENAME`

- `user_nl_clm` is identical to that used in `amip-p4k`. `user_nl_clm` was copied directly from `amip-p4k` run into the `amip-lwoff` staging directory. See

`$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_files/$CASENAME`

- A modified version of

`$CESMROOT/components/cam/src/physics/rrtmg/radiation.F90`

was staged in

`$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/$CASENAME/SourceMods/src.cam.`

Note: The modified version of `radiation.F90` contains the source code changes that allow "lwoff" (make clouds invisible to LW radiation). Note that the `SourceMods/src.cam` directory tree MUST be staged in this way, otherwise the model will fail at the build.

- `create_cylc_newcase_*` (alternate method to modify namelist settings during `create_newcase` step... other method is through `user_nl_*` in `user-mods-dir`)
 - `cesm_xml` settings were taken from `amip-p4k` case (`$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc/CESM-WF_tier1/create_cylc_newcase_cf mip_amip-p4k`). Note that `CAM_CONFIG_OPTS` was added to include the "-cosp" option. In piSST, the setting is "`CAM_CONFIG_OPTS = -phys cam6 -co2_cycle -cosp`", but for `amip-lwoff` I removed `-co2_cycle` as it is not needed (per `CAM_CONFIG_OPTS` in `amip-p4k`). Note that `docosp = .true.` in `user_nl_cam`, which is likely redundant with the `CAM_CONFIG_OPTS` setting. Note also that `CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS: "co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true."` was NOT set as it does not appear in `amip-p4k`'s `env_run.xml` or in the related `create_cylc_newcase` script.

● **amip-p4k-lwoff**

- **Directive:** "As for the `amip-p4k` experiment, but with cloud-radiative effects switched off in the LW radiation code."
- **Notes:**
 - Uses the same modified version of `radiation.F90` as in `amip-lwoff`.
 - For issues related to COSP with "lwoff", see `amip-lwoff` notes above.
- **Related case(s):**

- **amip (DECK):**
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CMIP6-AMIP.001
 - **amip-p4k (CFMIP):**
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-p4k.001
 - **amip-lwoff (CFMIP):** see above
 - **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name:
f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-p4k-lwoff.001
 - Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_amip-lwoff --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-p4k-lwoff.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset FHIST_BGC --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-p4k-lwoff.001
```
 - **Configuration settings**
 - user_bc_files
 - SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME will be identical to that used in amip-p4k. See \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/\$CASENAME
 - user_init_files: No modifications needed to initialization files (default is acceptable)
 - user_namelist_modifications
 - user_nl_cam and user_nl_cam are identical to the ones used in amip-lwoff. See \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_files/\$CASENAME
 - A modified version of \$CESMROOT/components/cam/src/physics/rrtmg/radiation.F90 was staged in \$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/\$CASENAME/SourceMods/src.cam.
Note: The modified version of radiation.F90 contains the source code changes that allow "lwoff" (make clouds invisible to LW radiation). Note that the SourceMods/src.cam directory tree MUST be staged in this way, otherwise the model will fail at the build.
 - create_cylc_newcase_* (alternate method to modify certain namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir). Located in: \$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc/CESM-WF_tier2
 - cesm_xml settings are identical to those for amip-lwoff, with one important exception: SSTICE_DATA_FILENAME must point to file

```
$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_bc_files/$CASENAME/cfmip_sst_p4k_HadOI  
Bl_bc_0.9x1.25_1850_2017_c20190129.nc
```

● aqua-control-lwoff

- **Directive:** "As for the aqua-control experiment, but with cloud-radiative effects switched off in the LW radiation code."
- **Notes:**
 - Uses the same modified version of radiation.F90 as in `amip-lwoff`.
 - For issues related to COSP with "lwoff", see `amip-lwoff` notes above.
- **Related case(s):**
 - **aqua-control:**
 - `/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-control.001`
 - **amip-lwoff:**
`$ARCHROOT/case_directories/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-lwoff.001`
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: `$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`
 - Case name: `f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-control-lwoff.001`
 - `Create_newcase` command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_aqua-control-lwoff --case  
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-control-  
lwoff.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset QPC6 --user-mods-dir  
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.QPC6.  
f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-control-lwoff.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - `user_bc_files`: No modifications needed to boundary conditions files (default is acceptable)
 - `user_init_files`: No modifications needed to initialization files (default is acceptable)
 - `user_namelist_modifications`
 - `aqua-control-lwoff`'s `user_nl_cam` is nearly identical to that used in `aqua-control`, except I explicitly activated COSP (`docosp = .true.`) and changed the following (**NOTE: There appear to be -no- lwoff-related changes needed in `user_nl_cam`**):
 - `fincl1`: Added Z500:A, OMEGA500:A
 - `fincl2`: Added U850:A, V850:A, U200:A, V200:A, FSNT:A, FSNTC:A
 - `user_nl_cam` was copied directly from the `aqua-control` run into the `aqua-control-lwoff` staging directory, and then the above changes were made

- A modified version of

`$CESMROOT/components/cam/src/physics/rrtmg/radiation.F90`

was staged in

`$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/$CASENAME/SourceMods/src.cam`

Note1: For aquaplanet, check that all but `src.cam` are removed from SourceMods tree because not all model components are in use

Note2: The modified version of `radiation.F90` contains the source code changes that allow "lwoff" (make clouds invisible to LW radiation). Note that the `SourceMods/src.cam` tree MUST be staged in this way, otherwise the model will fail at the build.

- `create_cylc_newcase_*` (alternate method to modify namelist settings during `create_newcase` step... other method is through `user_nl_*` in `user-mods-dir`)
 - The file itself was copied from the `amip-lwoff` version, but the `cesm_xml` settings were taken from the `aqua-control` case (`$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc/CESM-WF_tier1/create_cylc_newcase_cfmip_aqua-control`). I used `CAM_CONFIG_OPTS` identical to `aqua-control`: `CAM_CONFIG_OPTS = -phys cam6 -cosp -aquaplanet`". Note that option "`-co2_cycle`" was `-not-` included... for all prescribed-SST CFMIP simulations, `CCSM_BGC` in `env_run.xml` is set to "CO2A", and the same is true in `aqua-control`. Note also that `docosp = .true.` in `user_nl_cam`, which is likely redundant with the `CAM_CONFIG_OPTS` setting. Note also that `CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS`: "`co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true.`" was NOT set as it does not appear in `aqua-control`'s `user_nl_cam`, `env_run.xml` or in the related `create_cylc_newcase` script.

- **aqua-p4k-lwoff**

- **Directive:** "As for with the aqua-p4K experiment, but with cloud-radiative effects switched off in the LW radiation code."
- **Notes:**
 - Uses the same modified version of `radiation.F90` as in `amip-lwoff`.
 - For issues related to COSP with "lwoff", see `amip-lwoff` notes above.
- **Related case(s):**
 - **aqua-p4k:**
 - `/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-p4k.001`
 - **aqua-control-lwoff:** see above

○ **Case details:**

- Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
- Case name: f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-p4k-lwoff.001
- Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_aqua-p4k-lwoff --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-p4k-lwo
ff.001 --res f09_f09_mg17 --compset QPC6 --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/f.e21.QPC6.
f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-p4k-lwoff.001
```

○ **Configuration settings**

- user_bc_files: No modifications needed to boundary conditions files because SST+4K is implemented analytically via SourceMods... see "user_namelist_modifications" section below.
- user_init_files: No modifications needed to initialization files (default is acceptable)
- user_namelist_modifications

- Simply use aqua-control-lwoff's version of user_nl_cam (see above case notes for output variable selections)
- A modified version of

\$CESMROOT/components/cam/src/physics/rrtmg/radiation.F90
was staged in

\$ARCHROOT/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/\$CASENAME/SourceMods/src.cam

Note1: For aquaplanet, check that all but src.cam are removed from SourceMods tree because not all model components are in use

Note2: The modified version of radiation.F90 contains the source code changes that allow "lwoff" (make clouds invisible to LW radiation). Note that the SourceMods/src.cam tree MUST be staged in this way, otherwise the model will fail at the build.

- The modified version of /glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp007/cime/src/components/data_comps/docn/docn_comp_mod.F90 with SST+4K implemented must be staged in SourceMods. To do this, I located aqua-p4k's modified version of docn_comp_mod.F90 and diff-ed it with the cesm2.1-exp007 original version:

```
cd
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-aqua-p4K
.001/SourceMods/src.docn
> diff docn_comp_mod.F90
/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp007/cime/src/components/
data_comps/docn/docn_comp_mod.F90
841,843d840
< ! CFMIP +4K:
< sst = sst +4.0_r8
<
```

This confirms that the only changes to docn_comp_mod.F90 are

those related to increasing the SST by 4K uniformly. Then, copy directory

```
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/f.e21.QPC6.f09_f09_g17.CFMIP-aqua-p4K.001/SourceMods/src.docn to $CASEROOT/SourceMods
```

- **create_cylc_newcase_*** (alternate method to modify namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir)
 - Copied directly from aqua-control-lwoff (see `$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc/CESM-WF_tier2/create_cylc_newcase_aqua-control-lwoff`)
 - See additional details in aqua-control-lwoff case notes above.

● abrupt2xCO2

- **Directive:** "Identical to the DECK abrupt4xCO2, but at 2xCO2."
- **Notes:**
 - **Critical settings**
 - Repeat the abrupt4xCO2 case (use same compset), but adjust co2vmr as required...
 - `co2vmr = 1138.8e-6 → 569.4e-6` (set via `CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS` in `create_cylc_newcase_*` command, see below)
 - `'CAM_CONFIG_OPTS': '"-phys cam6 -co2_cycle -cosp"'`
 - `'CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS': '"co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true. co2vmr=569.4e-6"'`
 - `cesm_code_base =`
`'/gpfs/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/release-cesm2.1.0'`
- **Related case(s):**
 - **piControl (DECK):**
 - `/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-piControl.001`
 - **abrupt4xCO2 (DECK):**
 - `/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.BCO2x4cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt4xCO2.001`
- **Case details:**
 - **Case location:** `$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`
 - **Case name:** `b.e21.BCO2x2cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt2xCO2.001`
 - **Create_newcase command:**
`./create_cylc_newcase_abrupt2xCO2 --case`
`/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/b.e21.BCO2x2cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt2xCO2.001 --res f09_g17 --compset BCO2x4cmip6 --user-mods-dir`
`/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/b.e21.BCO2x2cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt2xCO2.001`
- **Configuration settings**

- PE layout note -- for new runs *with an appropriate env_mach_pes.xml file available*, simply add the desired env_mach_pes.xml file to user-mods-dirs and it will be used. Extreme care must be taken when modifying the PE layout as in some cases adding env_mach_pes.xml to user-mods-dirs did not work as expected. It is strongly recommended that the user carefully check env_mach_pes.xml prior to building the model and again prior to running the model.
- PE layout note -- particular to abrupt2xCO2 run in which *an appropriate env_mach_pes.xml file was not initially identified*: The default PE layout was too slow (completed 1 yr in 6 hrs). In the end, we ran the first 16 yr of abrupt2xCO2 using PE layout /glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/b.e21.BCO2x2cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt2xCO2.001/env_mach_pes.xml.piControl. We then changed the PE layout at this point to /glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/b.e21.BCO2x2cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt2xCO2.001/env_mach_pes.xml.fromCecile11feb2020 and continued using that until the end of the run. Note that changing the PE layout likely does not allow bit-for-bit reproducibility, but this was deemed not essential to abrupt2xCO2 as the climate state will not be changed significantly.
- user_bc_files: No modifications needed (default settings identical to those in abrupt4xCO2)
- user_init_files: No modifications needed to initialization files (default settings identical to those in abrupt4xCO2)
- user_namelist_modifications
 - No source code (SourceMods) changes required
 - For setups similar to abrupt2xCO2, copy desired env_mach_pes.xml file into user_namelist_modifications before building and running the model
 - Intention is to use same (or nearly the same) user_nl_* settings as in abrupt4xCO2 run. In user_nl_cam, "history_dust = .true." was removed.
- create_cylc_newcase_* (alternate method to modify namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir)
 - Copied from \$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc/CESM-WF_tier2/create_cylc_newcase_amip-piForcing with additional changes:
 - 'RESUBMIT': '74'
 - 'STOP_N': '2'
 - 'CAM_CONFIG_OPTS': '"-phys cam6 -co2_cycle -cosp"'
 - 'CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS': '"co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true.
co2vmr=569.4e-6"'
 - cesm_code_base =
'/gpfs/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/release-cesm2.1.0'

- Outputs: copy what was done for abrupt4xCO2

● abrupt0p5xCO2

- **Directive:** "Identical to the DECK abrupt4xCO2, but at 0.5xCO2."
- **Notes:**
 - **Critical settings**
 - Repeat the abrupt4xCO2 case (use same compset), but adjust co2vmr as required...
 - co2vmr = 1138.8e-6 → 142.35e-6 (set via CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS in create_cylc_newcase_* command, see below)
 - 'CAM_CONFIG_OPTS': '"-phys cam6 -co2_cycle -cosp"'
 - 'CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS': '"co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true.
co2vmr=142.35e-6"'
 - cesm_code_base =
'/gpfs/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/release-cesm2.1.0'
- **Related case(s):**
 - **abrupt2xCO2:** see case above
 - **piControl (DECK):**
 - /glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-piControl.001
 - **abrupt4xCO2 (DECK):**
 - /glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.BCO2x4cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt4xCO2.001
- **Case details:**
 - **Case location:** \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - **Case name:**
b.e21.BCO2x0p5cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt0p5xCO2.001
 - **Create_newcase command:**
./create_cylc_newcase_abrupt0p5xCO2 --case /glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/b.e21.BCO2x0p5cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt0p5xCO2.001 --res f09_g17 --compset BCO2x4cmip6 --user-mods-dir /gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/b.e21.BCO2x0p5cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt0p5xCO2.001
- **Configuration settings**
 - **user_bc_files:** No modifications needed (default settings identical to those in abrupt4xCO2 and abrupt2xCO2)
 - **user_init_files:** No modifications needed to initialization files (default settings identical to those in abrupt4xCO2 and abrupt4xCO2)
 - **user_namelist_modifications**
 - No source code (SourceMods) changes required
 - Add the desired env_mach_pes.xml file to user-mods-dirs:

- cd
 - /gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications
- mkdir b.e21.BCO2x0p5cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt0p5xCO2.001
- cd b.e21.BCO2x0p5cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt0p5xCO2.001
- cp
 - /glade/p/cesmdata/cseg/runs/cesm2_0/b.e20.B1850.f09_g17.pi_control.all.297_gamma_coef_t2_4XCO2/env_mach_pes.xml .
- Intention is to use same (or nearly the same) user_nl_* settings as in abrupt4xCO2 run. In user_nl_cam, "history_dust = .true." was removed.
- create_cylc_newcase_* (alternate method to modify namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir)
 - Copied from
 - \$ARCHROOT/scripts_cylc/CESM-WF_tier2/create_cylc_newcase_amip-piForcing with additional changes:
 - 'RESUBMIT': '74'
 - 'STOP_N': '2'
 - 'CAM_CONFIG_OPTS': '"-phys cam6 -co2_cycle -cosp"'
 - 'CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS': '"co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true.
co2vmr=142.35e-6"'
 - cesm_code_base =
 - '/gpfs/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/release-cesm2.1.0'
- Outputs: copy what was done for abrupt4xCO2

● abrupt-solp4p

- **Directive:** "Conceptually similar to the abrupt-4xCO2 DECK experiment, except that the solar constant rather than CO2 is abruptly increased by 4%."
- **Notes:**
 - Critical settings
 - Create_newcase: was copied from abrupt0p5CO2, then the following were modified:
 - Model version: Use piControl's model version as abrupt-solp4p will be directly compared to this version: `/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp003/`. Note that abrupt-4xCO2 used a different model version: `/gpfs/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/release-cesm2.1.0`
 - Compset: Use same compset as piControl but also ensure that abrupt-solp4p uses the same launch point (RUN_REFCASE and RUN_REFDATE) as abrupt-4xCO2.

- The PE layout can be modified to match that of abrupt[4,2,0p5]CO2, but it is strongly recommended NOT to do this via modifications to the create_newcase script
 - user_nl_cam in user-mods-dir: point to new solar file (see below). Use same outputs as abrupt-4xCO2.
 - Repeat the piControl case (use same compset), but make solar_irrad_data_file in CAM namelist point to a scaled version (+4% or -4%) of the version of the file shown for piControl.
 - 'CAM_CONFIG_OPTS': '"-phys cam6 -co2_cycle -cosp"'
 - 'CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS': '"co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true."'
- **Related case(s):**
 - **piControl (DECK):**
 - /glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-piControl.001
 - **abrupt4xCO2 (DECK):**
 - /glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.BCO2x4cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt4xCO2.001
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: \$ARCHROOT/case_directories/\$CASENAME
 - Case name: b.e21.B1850cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solp4p.001
 - Create_newcase command:

```
./create_cylc_newcase_abrupt-solp4p --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/b.e21.B1850cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solp
4p.001 --res f09_g17 --compset B1850 --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fsl/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/b.e21.B1850
cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solp4p.001
```
- **Configuration settings**
 - PE layout: It was discovered that the order in which the xmlchange commands are performed does -NOT- match the order in which they appear in the create_cylc_newcase script. This may result in undesired PE layout settings. It is strongly recommended that the user manually change the PE setting (in env_mach_pes.xml) -after- running create_cylc_newcase but before running case.setup.
 - user_bc_files: CESM2 uses an input file containing solar spectral irradiances (SSI), defined by CAM namelist variable solar_irrad_data_file. The solar constant (TSI) in CESM2 is diagnosed as the integral of SSI across wavelength and is not set directly by the user. Our approach to modify the solar irradiances for abrupt-solp4p is to scale the values contained within piControl's version of solar_irrad_data_file (/glade/p/cesmdata/cseg/inputdata/atm/cam/solar/SolarForcingCMIP6piControl_c160921.nc) by 4% using script \$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/solar/solar_scaler_CFMIP.py. The output file produced by this script is

SolarForcingCMIP6abrupt-solp4p_c200303.nc. In user_nl_cam, point solar_irrad_data_file to this file. Note: additional variables that this script neglects to include in the output file are only needed if WACCM is being used, which it is not for case abrupt-solp4p or abrupt-solm4p.

- user_init_files: No modifications needed to initialization files (default settings identical to those in abrupt[4,2,0.5]xCO2)
- user_namelist_modifications
 - No source code (SourceMods) changes required
 - Intention is to use same (or nearly the same) user_nl_* settings as in abrupt4xCO2 run. Check user_nl_* just before ./case.build to see how these files compare with abrupt4xCO2. Some important settings to check/edit:
 - In user_nl_cam, "history_dust = .true." was removed.
 - In user_nl_cam, the following line was added (or edited):

```
solar_irrad_data_file =  
'/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_bc_files/b.e21.B185  
0cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solp4p.001/SolarForcingCMIP6ab  
rupt-solp4p_c200303.nc'
```
- create_cylc_newcase_* (alternate method to modify namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir)
 - Copied from abrupt0.5xCO2 with additional changes:
 - Changed cesm_code_base to match piControl:

```
cesm_code_base =  
'/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp003/'
```
 - Immediately after running ./create_cylc_newcase, it is recommended that the user review env_mach_pes.xml and make any necessary changes.
 - For simulations using cesm_code_base =

```
'/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp003/',
```

IMMEDIATELY after running create_cylc_newcase the user may need to update env_mach_specific.xml to a new version in the case directory. An example of what was done for abrupt-solp4p:

```
cp  
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/b.e21.BCO2x2cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6  
-abrupt2xCO2.001/env_mach_specific.xml  
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/b.e21.B1850cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-  
abrupt-solp4p.001
```
- Outputs: copied what was done for abrupt[4,2,0.5]xCO2

● abrupt-solm4p

- **Directive:** "Conceptually similar to the abrupt-4xCO2 DECK experiment, except that the solar constant rather than CO2 is abruptly reduced by 4%."
- **Notes:**
 - **Critical settings**
 - **Create_newcase:** copy from abrupt0p5CO2, then modify the following:
 - **Model version:** Use piControl's model version as abrupt-solp4p will be directly compared to this version: `/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp003/`. Note that abrupt-4xCO2 used a different model version: `/gpfs/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/release-cesm2.1.0`
 - **Compset:** Use same compset as piControl but also ensure that abrupt-solp4p uses the same launch point (RUN_REFCASE and RUN_REFDATE) as abrupt-4xCO2.
 - The PE layout can be modified to match that of abrupt[4,2,0p5]CO2, but it is strongly recommended NOT to do this via modifications to the create_newcase script
 - **user_nl_cam** in user-mods-dir: point to new solar file (see below). Use same outputs as abrupt-4xCO2.
 - Repeat the piControl case (use same compset), but make `solar_irrad_data_file` in CAM namelist point to a scaled version (+4% or -4%) of the version of the file shown for piControl.
 - `'CAM_CONFIG_OPTS': '"-phys cam6 -co2_cycle -cosp"'`
 - `'CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS': '"co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true."'`
 - **Related case(s):**
 - **abrupt-solp4p:** see case above
 - **piControl (DECK):**
 - `/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-piControl.001`
 - **abrupt4xCO2 (DECK):**
 - `/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/b.e21.BCO2x4cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt4xCO2.001`
 - **Case details:**
 - **Case location:** `$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`
 - **Case name:** `b.e21.B1850cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solm4p.001`
 - **Create_newcase command:**

```
./create_cylc_newcase_abrupt-solm4p --case
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/b.e21.B1850cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solm
4p.001 --res f09_g17 --compset B1850 --user-mods-dir
/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_namelist_modifications/b.e21.B1850
cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solm4p.001
```
 - **Configuration settings**

- PE layout: It was discovered that the order in which the xmlchange commands are performed does -NOT- match the order in which they appear in the create_cylc_newcase script. This may result in undesired PE layout settings. It is strongly recommended that the user manually change the PE setting (in env_mach_pes.xml) -after- running create_cylc_newcase but before running case.setup.
- user_bc_files: CESM2 uses an input file containing solar spectral irradiances (SSI), defined by CAM namelist variable solar_irrad_data_file. The solar constant (TSI) in CESM2 is diagnosed as the integral of SSI across wavelength and is not set directly by the user. Our approach to modify the solar irradiances for abrupt-solm4p is to scale the values contained within piControl's version of solar_irrad_data_file (/glade/p/cesmdata/cseg/inputdata/atm/cam/solar/SolarForcingCMIP6piControl_c160921.nc) by -4% using script \$ARCHROOT/input_support_files/solar/solar_scaler_CFMIP.py. The output file produced by this script is SolarForcingCMIP6abrupt-solm4p_c200303.nc. In user_nl_cam, point solar_irrad_data_file to this file. Note: additional variables that this script neglects to include in the output file are only needed if WACCM is being used, which it is not for case abrupt-solp4p or abrupt-solm4p.
- user_init_files: No modifications needed to initialization files (default settings identical to those in abrupt[4,2,0.5]xCO2)
- user_namelist_modifications
 - No source code (SourceMods) changes required
 - Intention is to use same (or nearly the same) user_nl_* settings as in abrupt4xCO2 run. Check user_nl_* just before ./case.build to see how these files compare with abrupt4xCO2. Some important settings to check/edit:
 - In user_nl_cam, "history_dust = .true." was removed.
 - In user_nl_cam, the following line was added (or edited):


```
solar_irrad_data_file =
'/gpfs/fs1/work/cmip6/cases/CFMIP/user_bc_files/b.e21.B185
0cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-solm4p.001/SolarForcingCMIP6ab
rupt-solm4p_c200303.nc'
```
- create_cylc_newcase_* (alternate method to modify namelist settings during create_newcase step... other method is through user_nl_* in user-mods-dir)
 - Copied from abrupt-solp4p with additional changes...
 - Changed cesm_code_base to match piControl:


```
cesm_code_base = '/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp003/'
```
 - Important "xml" changes in create_cylc_newcase_abrupt-solm4p:


```
'CAM_NAMELIST_OPTS': '"co2_cycle_rad_passive=.true."',
'RUN_REFCASE':
```

```
'b.e21.B1850.f09_g17.CMIP6-piControl.001',
  'RUN_REFDATE': '0501-01-01',
  'GLC2ICE_RMAPNAME': 'idmap_ignore',
  'MPIRUN_RETRY_REGEX': 'MPI_LAUNCH_TIMEOUT'
```

- Not sure if the last two lines are strictly required
- Immediately after running `./create_cylc_newcase`, it is recommended that the user review `env_mach_pes.xml` and make any necessary changes.
- For simulations using `cesm_code_base =`

```
'/glade/u/home/cmip6/cesm_tags/cesm2.1-exp003/', IMMEDIATELY
after running create_cylc_newcase the user may need to update
env_mach_specific.xml to a new version in the case directory. An
example of what was done for abrupt-solp4p:
cp
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/b.e21.BC02x2cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt
2xCO2.001/env_mach_specific.xml
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/b.e21.B1850cmip6.f09_g17.CMIP6-abrupt-
solp4p.001
```

- Outputs: copy what was done for abrupt[4,2,0.5]xCO2

● amip-m4k

- **Directive:** "As for the amip experiment, but SSTs are subject to a uniform cooling of 4K."
- **Note:** Configured and run by Brian Medeiros. See the following case directory for guidance:

```
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-m4k.001
```
- **Related case(s):**
 - **amip (DECK):**

```
/glade/work/cmip6/cases/DECK/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CMIP6-AMIP.001
```
 - **amip-p4k (CFMIP):**

```
$ARCHROOT/case_directories/f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-p4k.001
```
- **Case details:**
 - Case location: `$ARCHROOT/case_directories/$CASENAME`
 - Case name: `f.e21.FHIST_BGC.f09_f09_mg17.CFMIP-amip-m4k.001`